

The Theory of Noema: Genetic Power and Information Creation in Computational Systems

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Abstract

Meaning is fundamental to understanding the relationship between information and cognition, yet its quantification remains elusive in computational systems. This paper introduces a multidimensional framework, the *Theory of Noema*, which redefines meaning as the interplay of four key parameters: relevance ($R(f)$), utility ($U(f)$), creativity ($C(f)$), and genetic power ($G(f)$). Unlike static measures, this framework treats meaning as a dynamic interaction that can be applied to artificial intelligence, natural language processing, and pattern recognition. The theory is mathematically formalized and opens avenues for future implementation in real-world, adaptive systems.

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1 Introduction

Noema is the Greek word for meaning. However, its semantic depth and ancient roots in the word *nous* provide an entirely different perspective compared to the word *meaning*. While I find this differentiation intriguing enough to contrast *noema* with *meaning*, further exploration of this philosophical and linguistic topic would be beyond the scope of the mathematical framework of this paper. Therefore, for the purposes of understanding the proposed theory, consider *noema* synonymous with *meaning*, and the two terms will be used interchangeably.

What is meaning? This question has remained fundamental from ancient philosophy to the dawn of the space age. Attempting to avoid dead-end inquiries, we observe that at the core of our existence, meaning is, among other things, the bridge that connects information with understanding. However, while the human mind tends to assign meaning to every signal, computational systems remain bound by simple analytical processes. Confronted with such challenges, I deemed it necessary to propose a multidimensional framework capable of defining, measuring, and integrating meaning in a way that reflects the creativity and dynamism of real life.

In today's world, data is produced at an accelerated pace. From images and videos to natural language processing, computational systems are commissioned not only to analyze but also to create information. However, how can a system discern what is meaningful? How can it measure relevance, usefulness, or even the creativity of a signal? This challenge remains open, leaving room for a new mathematical and practical theory.

In this article, I present the "Theory of Noema: Genetic Power and Information Creation" - a multidimensional framework that redefines the concept of meaning for computational and dynamic systems. We introduce four key parameters: Relevance ($R(f)$), Utility ($U(f)$), Creativity ($C(f)$), and Genetic Power ($G(f)$). Through this approach, meaning ($N(f)$) is defined not as a one-dimensional quantity but as an emergence from a vibrant set of interactions that can be applied to artificial intelligence, natural language processing, and pattern recognition.

In this article, we explore mostly the theoretical foundations of the theory, but also its potential practical applications, paving the way for its integration into real-world systems that learn, evolve, and create. But, before we move on to the theoretical model, I ought to thank Pavlos Tomazos, an Informatics student at the University of Athens and a good old friend, without the help of whom this theory would be less developed and completed.

2 Theoretical Model

2.1 Noema ($N(f)$)

The Noema of a signal f is defined as its combined value across four key dimensions:

- **Relevance** ($R(f)$): The degree to which the signal relates to a given need S .
- **Utility** ($U(f)$): The degree to which the signal contributes to the achievement of the goal represented by the need S .
- **Creativity** ($C(f)$): The differentiation and originality of the signal.
- **Genetic Power** ($G(f)$): The ability of the signal to generate new information and dynamically influence the system.

The fundamental equation of noema is:

$$N(f) = (R(f) \cdot U(f) + \alpha \cdot C(f)) \cdot G(f),$$

where:

- α : A weighting factor for creativity $C(f)$.

2.2 Relevance ($R(f)$)

Relevance measures how closely the signal f relates to the need S . It is defined as:

$$R(f) = 1 - \frac{D(f, S)}{D_{\max}},$$

where:

- $D(f, S)$: The distance (e.g., Euclidean or cosine) between the signal and the need.
- $D_{\max}$: The maximum distance possible within the given context.

2.2.1 Analyzing the Need (S)

The need S represents an ideal/expected pattern or target against which the signal f is compared. Depending on the application, it can take various forms.

Static and Dynamic Needs:

- **Static Need:** When S remains constant and represents a predefined pattern or goal (e.g., an ideal high-resolution image).
- **Dynamic Need:** When S changes over time or depends on external factors. In this case, S can be defined as a function of time, $S(t)$.

Mathematical Representations of the Need (S):

- **Fixed Vector:** S can be a fixed vector or template representing the ideal state.
- **Time Function:** $S(t)$, for dynamic environments where the need changes over time.
- **Probability:** S may be expressed as a probability $P(X)$, where $P(X)$ is the likelihood that a signal X belongs to the ideal state.
- **Minimal Distance:** $S = \arg \min_{x \in X} D(f, x)$, where $D(f, x)$ is the Euclidean distance measuring how close the signal f is to the reference data X .

Interpretation: The need S serves as a reference point to evaluate the signal f . It can be static or dynamic depending on the system's requirements and can be described mathematically in various ways to adapt to different application domains.

2.3 Utility ($U(f)$)

Utility measures the practical performance of the signal in meeting the need. It is defined as:

$$U(f) = \frac{P(f)}{P_{\max}},$$

where:

- $P(f)$: The performance of the signal (for example, the accuracy of a classifier).
- $P_{\max}$: The maximum possible performance.

2.4 Creativity ($C(f)$)

Creativity measures the originality of the signal by calculating its differentiation from training data. It is defined as:

$$C(f) = \frac{\text{Var}(f)}{\text{Var}_{\max}},$$

where:

- $\text{Var}(f)$: The variability of the signal.
- $\text{Var}_{\max}$: The maximum possible variability.

2.5 Genetic Power ($G(f)$)

Genetic power measures the signal's ability to generate new information and dynamically influence the system. It is defined as:

$$G(f) = 1 + \gamma \cdot \frac{\partial I}{\partial t},$$

where:

- I : The information produced by the system.
- $\frac{\partial I}{\partial t}$: The rate of change of information over time.
- γ : A sensitivity coefficient.

Normalized Function: The normalized function $\tilde{g}(f)$ can be expressed as:

$$\tilde{g}(f) = \frac{g(f) - g_{\min}}{g_{\max} - g_{\min}},$$

where:

- $g(f)$: The original function describing the genetic power of the signal f .
- $g_{\max}$ and $g_{\min}$: The maximum and minimum possible values of $g(f)$ in the given context.

3 Conclusions and Future Work

3.1 Conclusions

The *Theory of Noema* presented in this work provides a new, multidimensional framework for understanding and quantifying meaning in computational systems. By combining four key parameters:

- **Relevance** ($R(f)$): The connection of the signal to a specific need.
- **Utility** ($U(f)$): The practical performance of the signal.
- **Creativity** ($C(f)$): The originality and differentiation of the signal.
- **Genetic Power** ($G(f)$): The ability of the signal to generate new information and dynamically influence the system.

The theory redefines meaning not as a static property but as the result of a dynamic interaction of these parameters.

3.2 Final Thoughts

The *Theory of Noema* is not just a new scientific approach but also a pathway toward the gradual unification of broad theoretical thought with the applicability of computational systems. This work lays the foundation for further exploration and implementation in practical domains. It is crucial to underline that the four parameters are not meant to be exhaustive. Over time, additional functions may be introduced, unveiling new dimensions and expanding the theory into a more intricate framework. The appendix outlines a pathway toward this goal. However, before venturing into more complex approaches, it is logical and prudent to first present the initial theoretical framework to the world and the scientific community. This step is essential for its evaluation — whether it is to confirm, refine, or challenge the theory. For the ultimate purpose, the first and the last, is to contribute to the advancement of human thought and understanding. This simple theory, I hope, is but a small spark toward that greater purpose.

4 Appendix: Hierarchy of Values in the Symbolic World

Idea and Objective: As described in the main framework, meaning emerges from the combinatorial analysis of the four core parameters ($R(f)$, $U(f)$, $C(f)$, $G(f)$). However, in -psychologically speaking- symbolic systems where signals (e.g., words, images, concepts) are associated with multilayered values, meaning can also be described as the result of a hierarchy of these values. This section provides a mathematical description of how such a hierarchy can be incorporated into the theory.

Mathematical Description: Consider a symbolic world S consisting of n symbols, $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$. Each symbol s_i is described by a vector of properties:

$$s_i = [x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{ik}],$$

where x_{ij} represents the j -th property of s_i (e.g., utility, relevance, creativity).

1. **Normalization of Values:** Each property x_{ij} is normalized to the range $[0, 1]$:

$$\tilde{x}_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - x_{\min,j}}{x_{\max,j} - x_{\min,j}}.$$

2. **Definition of Hierarchical Measure:** The overall value of a symbol s_i can be expressed as:

$$V(s_i) = \sum_{j=1}^k w_j \cdot \tilde{x}_{ij},$$

where w_j is the weighting factor for the j -th property and $\sum_{j=1}^k w_j = 1$.

3. **Ranking of Symbols:** Symbols s_i are ranked based on $V(s_i)$ in descending order:

$$s_{(1)}, s_{(2)}, \dots, s_{(n)},$$

where $V(s_{(1)}) \geq V(s_{(2)}) \geq \dots \geq V(s_{(n)})$.

Applications:

- **Natural Language Processing (NLP):** Compute the relative importance of words in a text based on their properties.
- **Knowledge Graphs:** Identify key nodes based on hierarchical values.
- **Autonomous Systems:** Prioritize actions based on the hierarchy of options.